

**Let the
dialogue
begin**

D6.2 DISSEMINATION STRATEGY & ACTION PLAN

Project: **Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management**

Acronym: **Firelogue**

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	101036534	Acronym	Firelogue
Full Title	Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management		
Start Date	01/11/2021	Duration	48 months
Project URL	https://firelogue.eu/		
Deliverable	D6.2 Dissemination Strategy and Action Plan		
Work Package	WP6 Dissemination and Insights Upscaling		
Date of Delivery	Contractual	31/03/2022	Actual 31/03/2022
Nature	Report	Dissemination Level	Public
Lead Beneficiary	NOA		
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Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
v_0.1	03/03/2022	Draft	Draft for Review	Jorge Gomes (VOST Portugal) Sofia Oikonomou (EDGE)
v_0.2	14/03/2022	Draft	The Draft was sent to the consortium for comments. Minor changes were done in the target groups.	Maïke Overmeyer (FhG) Sofia Oikonomou (EDGE) Jean Paul Monnet (TIEMS)
v_1	22/03/2022	Final	Format changes applied.	Maïke Overmeyer (FhG) Sofia Oikonomou (EDGE)

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
D	Deliverable
DOW	Description of Work
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
IA	Innovation Action
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NOA	National Observatory of Athens
T	Task
WFRM	Wildfire risk management
WP	Work package

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the dissemination and communication strategy of the Firelogue project. In order to ensure that the various outputs of Firelogue are appropriately disseminated amongst the interested stakeholders, this Deliverable specifies the dissemination strategy.

The related measures are presented in detail in this document, whilst references are made to D6.1 Communication Strategy & Action Plan. Firelogue is committed to ensure that the results of the project are made available and accessible to a wide community of stakeholders across the various sectors targeted by the project.

Firelogue will use a variety of dissemination tools/activities to reach all audiences. These include among others a website, published articles and presentation of the project to conferences outcomes and objectives, events and workshops as presented in detail in this document.

1 Introduction

Dissemination is a horizontal activity and concentrates on disseminating the results of Firelogue to a wide range of existing or potential stakeholders. Firelogue's dissemination strategy has a strong European and international focus. It details how project partners are supplied with information on external meetings and scientific conferences related to the project objectives, other projects, and initiatives, as well as different possibilities to disseminate project results to relevant audiences.

Firelogue will create impact not only through dissemination and communication activities, but also by linking with other initiatives and networks, in close cooperation with WP7 for Stakeholder Engagement and interacting with national key actors responsible for WFRM and upscaling of project results into international fora.

A series of dissemination actions regarding the best possible dissemination of Firelogue's outputs in all stakeholders are mentioned in this document.

These actions are thoroughly presented in the current document while references are made to D6.1 Communication Strategy & Action Plan. We will ensure that the project results will be made available and accessible to a wide community of stakeholders across the various sectors targeted by the project.

The dissemination plan will:

- Shape the project's dissemination goals and define the target audiences;
- Highlight project dissemination principles to be followed by project partners within the project's lifetime;
- Link the adequate dissemination tools per each target group according to key messages;
- Outline short to long-term dissemination objectives to support the impact of the project beyond its lifetime;
- Work through key messages and define the best possible dissemination channels.

As stated in the Grant Agreement, this document is dynamic and will be updated throughout the duration of the project. In that sense, the indicated activities are not exhaustive. More inputs will be added over time and more specifically during the WP6 Deliverable's revisions at Months 24 (D6.5) and Month 36 (D6.6).

2 Dissemination Goals

Firelogue aims to create a dialogue and empower the WFRM community to face the current and future wildfire challenges. Firelogue is going to act as an exchange enabler of knowledge through the aggregation of experience and best practices of all stakeholders. Firelogue's mission is to create a space and the conditions to boost communication within the WFRM community and society, as well as to retain and share the knowledge and the experiences gathered alongside the showcase of innovative actions and products.

To achieve this goal, a coherent dissemination strategy is needed. The Dissemination Strategy is part of Firelogue's WP6 "Dissemination and insight upscaling" and its main objective is to ensure that Firelogue's impact is maximised through an effective communication and dissemination campaign, supported by engagement activities.

The main dissemination goals are to use Firelogue as a communication channel to connect and empower the WFRM community by disseminating the technological solutions developed by the Innovation Actions (IAs). Moreover, dissemination strategy ensures that Firelogue becomes known to key stakeholders, including Policy/ Decision Makers, Scientific Community, Civil Society, Media, Local and Regional Authorities, Fire and Rescue Services and Industry, as well as generates active interest and encourages potential users to experience Firelogue and its output, through active participation in workshops, conferences and other events, building on the Firelogue website and Communication Booster.

The Firelogue dissemination action plan is built on the following principles:

- Participation in dedicated **conferences/workshops/seminars**: Partner representatives will participate in scientific conferences, seminars and Dialogue Workshops related to the Firelogue objectives. Their presentations should focus both on promoting project outcomes and activities and on contributing to the stakeholder's engagement. Where of interest, presentations should include results on the activities undertaken within the IAs. A series of dedicated events have already been scheduled for Firelogue partners to participate in throughout the duration of 2022:
 - WFRM Clustering Event (April 2022): Firelogue will be the facilitator of the WFRM Clustering Event, organised by the European Commission that will be held on 5-6 April 2022 and will bring together Firelogue, [FirEUrisk](#), the three Innovation Actions, and other related projects such as [FireLinks](#), [FIRE-IN](#) and [SAFERS](#). WP6 will support all the partners at these events with dedicated communication material, an indicative communication plan and a social media action plan will be distributed to related partners to maximise the impact of the event.
 - [ISCRAM Conference](#) (May 2022, Tarbes): Firelogue, the IAs and [FirEUrisk](#) will hold joint sessions organised by the [SAFERS](#) project. The workshop session will focus on Big Data and AI trends of crisis management.
 - Aerial Firefighting Conference (May 2022, Nimes): Firelogue will organise a session at the conference, involving the IAs and [FirEUrisk](#), most likely focusing on the technological innovations the projects develop in relation to aerial firefighting including the use of drones.
 - [International Conference on Forest Fire Research](#) (November 2022, Coimbra): Firelogue will actively contribute to the ICFFR in various ways that are on discussion

with the organiser ADAI, a key partner in Firelogue. Some initial ideas on Firelogue's contribution are: (i) organization of an EU Project Session, (ii) organization of a "Multi-stakeholder challenges in managing wildfire risk" session and (iii) contribution to the proceedings of the Conference. Additionally, Firelogue supports the creation of a dedicated conference application to connect and involve the participants.

Finally, it is essential to note that a calendar including all the events of Firelogue, the IAs, [FirEURisk](#) but also additional conferences and workshops of interest will be displayed on the Firelogue website. All the events that Firelogue will participate in 2022 can be found in Table 5.

- **Publications:** Firelogue will actively pursue the dissemination of Firelogue's and IAs' results to the targeted audiences (Section 2.2). The designated dissemination plan is expected to emphasise on: i) publications in peer reviewed journals, ii) articles in media and magazines, iii) presentations at International Conferences, (iv) encourage and support joint scientific publications between the Innovation Actions (T2.4: Joint Publication and White Paper Development).

Indicatively, Firelogue's publications can be presented in the following journals (not exhaustive list), but a more comprehensive list will be provided when stakeholders from Firelogue and IA will be consulted:

- International Journal of Emergency Management;
- International Journal of Disaster Risk Management;
- International Journal of Disaster Risk Sciences;
- Journal of International Crisis and Risk;
- Disasters;
- Fire Safety;
- Disaster Prevention and Management;
- International Journal of Wildland Fire.
- The **Communication Booster**, which will coordinate the engagement between Firelogue and IAs will be further defined in the project lifecycle building on the discussions with IAs. Specifications will be given at the Deliverable D6.4 "User Engagement and Dissemination Support tool and Strategy".

2.1 Timing

Through this dissemination plan, the target audiences will get to know the project activities and its results and will ensure an improved understanding of the Firelogue exploitation needs. In that regard, the project has defined a number of short, medium and long-term objectives summarised below:

Short-term dissemination activities (M01 - M20)

- Raise awareness on project objectives and expected outcomes;
- Disseminate IAs activities and goals;
- Disseminate Firelogue platform among the various stakeholders and WFRM community;
- Introducing the project to the wider public.

Medium term dissemination activities (M20 - M36)

- Disseminate information on IAs development and outcomes;

- Promote IAs results, services, etc.;
- Extend the project's reputation beyond partnering countries;
- Disseminate messages on the benefits of improving communication among users and providers of WFRM services and products.

Long term dissemination activities (> M36)

- Promote Firelogue services and tools after the completion of the project;
- Encourage a sustainable long-term cooperation among partners and external stakeholders and users;
- Promoting the integrated IA and [FirEUrisk](#) results and recommendations facilitated by Firelogue to European Institutions;
- Promote Firelogue website and Communication Booster as a sustainable tool of communication.

2.2 Target Audiences

To reinforce the uptake of the Firelogue results and services, the dissemination plan is designed focusing on the following target audiences:

1. **Policy/ Decision Makers and EU Institutions:** Firelogue will establish a communication platform where end-users will be able to find information on how wildfire services and data can support their line of work. The Firelogue website will offer end-users the chance to be informed about the activities undertaken within the IAs and connect with service providers. Firelogue incubates fire-prevention services designed with and for the users. The aim of the outreach to policymakers is to give them access to information so as for them to validate and make use of Firelogue recommendations and facilitate the adoption of the guidance from Firelogue.
2. **Scientific Community:** Support research and academic institutions within, and outside, the consortium by promoting their skills and capacities, exchange knowledge on specific thematic areas (i.e. in relation to the IAs), and finally create synergies with other actors in the value chain and with other initiatives. The aim of the outreach to the scientific community is to provide them with scientific data through the publications so as for them to use this knowledge for further research in the field.
3. **Civil Society:** The Firelogue website will provide easily understandable information on the socio-economic and environmental benefits of fire- prevention services and applications in the areas covered by the IAs. The project brings together a unique team of experts with the aim to enhance the exploitation of fire-prevention information services towards informed decision-making. Increased access to information aims at bringing forward issues that civil society can make use in local or regional level.
4. **Media:** Firelogue consists of 15 partners and engages several stakeholders in different countries. Through national and local media, and taking advantage of already established communication channels by each individual partner, the project will establish a media presence that will present Firelogue to a broader audience. The Firelogue website will also include information about relevant and current news on WFRM that can be used by media outlets, in the format of press releases. A basic problem of local media is the lack of information regarding European policies against WFRM. Firelogue, by providing this kind of information and by highlighting the results of all the projects will help towards this direction.

5. **Local and Regional Authorities:** Firelogue will share knowledge, information, and best practices that can be useful and implemented in their respective activities, directly and via already established channels by Firelogue's partners. By targeting local and regional authorities, we aim to provide them with the adequate information so as Firelogue recommendations to be adapted in local and regional level.
6. **Fire and Rescue Services:** Firelogue will raise awareness to the fact that wildfire services and solutions can be a cost-effective source of a wide-variety of valuable data. Fire and Rescue Services can benefit from these innovations, making their work more efficient.
7. **Industry:** New and innovative products and solutions will be developed by the IAs that can enhance wildfires' four stages of action: prevention, preparedness, restoration and adaptation giving the Industry important feedback on the real needs that exist and that can be exploited. This feedback is needed by the industry in order for them to exploit the solutions and link research with the Industry.

All the above-mentioned target audiences are strongly inter connected to each other. One of the key objectives of Firelogue is to help towards the formulation of a WFRM community where activities and results will not be replicated. For instance, the scientific results will be promoted to the industry and the media will use showcases of fire and rescue services that will make use of Firelogue outputs.

2.3 Key Messages

The Dissemination action plan takes into consideration the main expected impacts of the project as described in the DoA and the dissemination needs of each IA. Key messages open the door to direct communication with our audience, because they bridge what our audience already knows and the way we try to lead them.

Key messages as developed by D6.1 and detailed in the table below will deliver to our audience the elements we want them to remember and react to. Following the identification of the main audiences and the expected impacts of Firelogue, the next task is to create customised communication messages, mottos, catch phrases and taglines. Indicatively, the plan is currently being put into action through the Firelogue website, flyers & social media by using headlines & captions such as: Let the dialogue begin, Let's talk about it.

Table 1 matches the key messages developed in Deliverable 6.1, with the target audiences (Section 2.2) and the appropriate Dissemination Channels to be used.

Table 1: Key Messages

No.	Key messages	Target audiences	Dissemination channels
1	A one stop repository for IAs publications, documents, and data – Firelogue Website and Communication Booster will provide documents and data that any stakeholder in interest can have access	Scientific Community Fire and Rescue Services	Website Communication booster
2	A connecting link between stakeholders and citizens – Firelogue through social media and website will contribute as a connecting link	Civil Society Policy/ Decision Makers and EU Institutions Fire and Rescue Services Local and Regional Authorities	Social media Newsletter Website Press releases
3	An informative platform for relevant and current wildfire related news – Firelogue by newsletters, conferences, workshops, articles etc. will be an informative factor for wildfire	Civil Society Policy/ Decision Makers and EU Institutions Fire and Rescue Services Media	Social media Newsletter Publications Presentations in Conferences Press releases
4	A "firemap" of where and when – Firelogue in cooperation with the IAs will be a firemap to the public. Person of interest will be able to follow satellite maps of forest regions (created by the IAs), a mobile app will be created by one IA to inform citizens for wildfires and provide the necessary information of how to act properly	Civil Society Policy/ Decision Makers and EU Institutions Scientific Community Fire and Rescue Services Local and Regional Authorities Industry Media	Website Communication booster Techmall Firelogue events
5	A Market Place of fire solutions and applications – Firelogue will create a Market for the Technologies IAs will develop	Policy/ Decision Makers and EU Institutions Scientific Community Fire and Rescue Services Local and Regional Authorities Industry	Website Communication booster Techmall Publications

3 Dissemination Channels and Tools

Project activities will be disseminated through a large variety of communication channels. Taking advantage of social media platforms' real-time nature, continuous engagement of the various stakeholders following the progress of the project, will be actively used to engage in dialogue. These tools are important to use as they broadcast messages to the wider public getting direct feedback from the audience, along with presentations, posters, promotional materials, organising or participating in embedded events that will be thoroughly communicated via press releases thus creating several communication cycles.

Inside Firelogue, regarding the partners' involvement, active collaboration (i.e. providing timely feedback and input) is crucial for the efficient use of the communication tools. Microsoft TEAMS is already used with the main goal to share quickly, effectively and easily all the required information, as well as avoid email traffic among the partners. Every month, the partners provide information to the Communication and Dissemination Team regarding dissemination indicators, e.g. Tweets, posts, news articles etc.

Outside Firelogue, regarding the facilitation and enhancement of the dissemination of the IAs, a list has been created including the responsible Communicators of the IAs to share communication and dissemination actions with them with an ultimate goal to multiply our channels and contacts. Initial meetings with them have been conducted, firstly with all IAs separately and one joint meeting including IAs and [FirEUrisk](#). Various issues have been discussed thoroughly, such as: (i) set up of bi-monthly regular meetings, (ii) creation of a joint motto, (iii) a template for joint presentation, (iv) a joint video and (v) other communication activities that are going to be implemented jointly. It is furthermore planned to also set-up a way to communicate through the Firelogue's platform with the IAs and [FirEUrisk](#) to easily share information and documents that are of relevance for all, specifically with respect to (joint) dissemination activities.

3.1 Dissemination Channels

As in the case of key messages to be used, our different targets groups will require different dissemination channels.

Project activities will be disseminated through a large variety of communication channels including: the website, social media channels, presentations, posters, promotional materials, organising or participating in embedded events, press releases, as well as the Firelogue communication booster, which is described more detailed in D6.4, and includes many key features, such as Platform Hub, Knowledge Hub, TechMall, and many more to be defined.

Table 2 provides an overview of the dissemination channels that will be used in the course of the project towards the engagement of different target groups (Section 2.2).

Table 2: Dissemination Channels

Audience	Dissemination channels
Fire and Rescue Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website - Newsletter • Social Media Channels • Presentations – Posters • Promotional materials • Firelogue events & Embedded events • Press releases • Publications in scientific journals (national and/ or regional and/ or national) • Communication Booster
Policy/ Decision Makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website - Newsletter • Social Media Channels • Presentations – Posters • Promotional materials • Firelogue events & Embedded events • Press releases
Local and Regional Authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website - Newsletter • Social Media Channels • Presentations – Posters • Promotional materials • Firelogue events & Embedded events • Press releases
Civil Society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Media Channels • Presentations during events • Communication Booster
Scientific Community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website - Newsletter • Social Media Channels • Presentations – Posters • Promotional materials • Firelogue events & Embedded events • Press releases • Publications in scientific journals (national and/ or regional and/ or national) • Communication Booster
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social Media Channels • Presentations • Press releases • Animation Videos
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Social Media Channels • Animation Videos • Exhibitions etc. • Communication Booster

3.2 Communication Booster

Firelogue, in its effort to connect services and stakeholders, will create a platform for overall communication. This platform will be an area of information, innovative solutions, and services developed by the IAs. This will provide a unique entry point into Firelogue's extended network and we will be able to distribute the IA results in a coordinated manner as well as to redirect any WFRM related requests to the IAs and additional WFRM stakeholders.

The goal of the Communication booster is to be used by a broad network of partners, collaborators and stakeholders within different areas of WFRM. It is developed to optimize IAs outcomes by facilitating the exchange of information among the actors, creating critical mass and avoiding duplications. Hence, it is significantly reducing the risk of developing and replicating similar systems and remove traditional organisational and geographical boundaries.

This stakeholder management is linked with clustering as well as with all Firelogue communication and dissemination activities and particularly the design of the Communication Booster via the Firelogue digital platform. In addition, the Communication Booster will provide a Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) section on WFRM. In close collaboration with the Firelogue partners, IAs, and EU stakeholders such as DRMKC, sustainable options to maintain the Firelogue platform, in the long run, will be sought. More information about the Communication Booster and the stakeholder's engagement can be found in Deliverable 6.4 "User Engagement and Dissemination Support Tool and Strategy".

Table 3: List of public deliverables related to Firelogue dissemination activities

D#	Deliverable Title	WP number	Lead author	Due Date for internal review
D6.1	Communication Strategy and Action Plan	WP6	NOA	31 January 2022
D7.2	Stakeholder Clustering Report I	WP7	PCF	28 February 2022
D6.2	Dissemination Strategy and Action Plan	WP6	NOA	28 February 2022
D6.3	Website	WP6	EDGE	31 March 2022
D6.4	User engagement and Dissemination Support tool strategy and set up	WP6	EDGE	31 March 2022
D3.1	Impact Assessment Methodology Harmonisation I	WP3	NOA	30 June 2022
D2.4	FIRELOGUE TechMall I	WP2	EDGE	31 March 2023
D3.2	Baseline Assessment Report	WP3	UAH	31 March 2023
D3.4	Impact Assessment Methodology Harmonisation II	WP3	NOA	30 September 2023
D6.5	Mid-term report on Communication, Dissemination, website, helpdesk and User Engagement Activities	WP6	EDGE	30 September 2023
D7.7	Stakeholder Clustering Report II	WP7	PCF	30 March 2023
D1.7	WFRM technologies and maturity indicators II	WP1	NOA	30 September 2024
D2.10	FIRELOGUE Tech Mall II	WP2	EDGE	30 September 2024
D2.5	Publications: Book, White Paper and Roadmap	WP2	EDGE	30 September 2025
D3.3	Impact Assessment Action Plan towards 2030	WP3	NOA	30 September 2025
D6.7	Final Report on Communication, Dissemination, Website, Helpdesk and User Engagement Activities	WP6	EDGE	30 September 2025

D6.8	Common Communication Booster applications	WP6	EDGE	30 September 2025
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3.3 Firelogue's partners responsibilities

As previously described, support from all partners inside Firelogue is essential, so all partners will have clear-cut responsibilities on actions they can support. Partners will be asked to cooperate actively for the use of these tools, as it is an active way of involvement and getting feedback from them about the project. More specifically, Work Package leaders and Working Group Leaders are expected to promote WP/WG-related news, outcomes, discussions and findings and an initial list of ideas is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Roles of responsibilities of WP leaders in the dissemination activities

Dissemination directions	WP / WG	WP leader
Consistencies and Inconsistencies of the WFRM approaches	WP1	IIASA
Integration of WFRM research finding	WP2	PCF
Call's Impact assessment methodology	WP3	NOA
Just Transition Concept	WP4	Fraunhofer
Conflict and synergies across working groups	WP5	TRI
User engagement	WP6	EDGE
Stakeholders management and network engagement	WP7	Fraunhofer
Citizen engagement	WG Society	VOST PT
Interrelations between wildfires and industrial facilities	WG Infrastructure	KEMEA
Reduction of the financial impact of disasters	WG Insurance	IIASA
Emergency management	WG Civil protection	TIEMS
Ecosystems' response to changing fire-prone conditions	WG Ecology	CTFC

Finally, yet importantly, all Firelogue partners should consider the following:

- All communication items and publications must include recognition of financing by the European Union and include the following text: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101036534. The EU cannot be responsible under any circumstances for the content of communication items prepared by project partners."
- All project deliverables, documents and presentations must be prepared using the provided deliverable document and PowerPoint presentation templates

4 Events Methodology and Upcoming Calendar

Firelogue partners and the Members of the Working Groups will be actively participating in events such as conferences, workshops, seminars; dialogues, meetings etc. (see Table 5 below). WP6 will put emphasis on supporting events that will enable stakeholders to communicate their messages. To maximise the impact and reach of the project, the dissemination team will seek to organise events in synergy with the Innovation Actions. As stated earlier in this document Firelogue partners will therefore also participate in external meetings and scientific conferences related to Firelogue objectives and to events organised by IAs and FirEURisk. Their presentations should focus on

promoting project outcomes and activities. The project partners are defining an event list for the duration of the project work in order to cover as much as possible public outreach and to distribute the information about the project. To ensure the visibility of the project, maximise the impact of the events and establish deeper relations WP6 will:

1. Support all the events with dedicated communication material;
2. Distribute an indicative communication plan to related partners at least one month before the event (depending of the nature's event);
3. Distribute social media action plan to the partners and the communicators before a major event, announcement etc.;
4. Create press releases for the event launch;
5. Announce the event on social media and Firelogue website;
6. Gain press coverage – where possible – and help to amplify the event beyond the Firelogue network.

Table 5: Events 2022

	Type of Event	Event	Date
1	Conference	UN SPIDER Bonn International Conference (virtual), Space-based Solutions for Disaster Management in Africa: Networks and Information, Technologies in times of crisis.	17 of November, 2021 (attended)
2	Conference	Agenda de la Reunión Regional de Expertos de ONU-SPIDER y CEPREDENAC para América Latina	23-25 of November, 2021 (attended)
3	Project team meeting	Nemausus Project - Second Team Meeting	1-2 of December, 2021 (attended)
4	Meeting	Community of European Research and Innovation for Security (CERIS)	23-25 March 2022
4	Meeting	WFRM Clustering Event	05-06 April, 2022
5	Conference / Meeting	International Forest Policy Meeting	27-29 of April, 2022
6	Conference	ICFBR2022	03-06 of May, 2022
7	Conference/ Exhibition	Aerial Firefighting and Search & Rescue Europe Conference and Exhibition	18.-20 of May 2022
8	Conference	19th international conference on information systems for crisis response and management (ISCRAM)	22 - 25 of May, 2022
9	Conference	Aerial Firefighting and Search & Rescue Europe	18-20 May 2022
11	Conference	Fire Protection Safety and Security 2022	May 2022
12	Exhibition	Interschutz Exhibition	20-25 of June, 2022
13	Workshop	IEEE 14th Image, Video, and Multidimensional Signal Processing Workshop Multimodal Analysis, Fusion and Retrieval of satellite images special session	26-29 of June 2022
14	EXPO	International Disaster Response Expo	27-28 of September 2022
15	Conference	TIEMS 2022 Annual Conference	Sep-Oct 2022
16	Conference	Current problems concerning forest protection 2022	October, 2022
17	Conference	Fire Ecology across Boundaries	4-7 October 2022

18	Conference	International Conference on Forest Fire Research	11-18 of November 2022
21	Conference	Firealarm and Fireprotection Conference	TBD, 2022

5 Evaluation

The main objective of WP6 Dissemination and insight upscaling, is to ensure that the impact of the Firelogue project will be maximised through an effective campaign of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

The impact of the communication activities is strongly tied to the success of the stakeholder engagement and dissemination activities. Appropriate indicators to assess the impact of dissemination and communication include: a) Visits/views and engagement of website and social media using tools such as “Google Analytics” b) Followers/connections, social media outreach, a popular indicator due to their widespread adoption; c) Number of scientific publications, academic citations, views in platforms like ResearchGate; d) Participation/attendance in workshops, conferences through Firelogue’s presentations or demonstrations.

The detailed analysis of the impact of the individual activities of the project will be carried out during the project as its activities develop. As an input to that end Table 6 summarises potential indicators.

Table 6: Evaluation KPIs (as described in GA)

Purpose	Indicator	Target (KPI)
Increase awareness of scientific results	Scientific publications (cross-IA)	Paper: 5 Conference proceedings: 1 Book: 1
	Presentations at International Conferences	20
	Articles in media and magazines	10
	Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals	7
Target a wide range of audience using tailored communication tools	Number of visits to the project website	15.000 unique visitors
	Followers on social networks	1000
	Communication material produced	Printed: 1 brochure, 200 copies; Digital: 100 e-banners, e-news etc.)
	YouTube Video Channel views	>1000

6 Next steps for effective dissemination

The current document provides an overview of the dissemination strategy for Firelogue, in accordance with its overall communication strategy (D6.1), presenting how project outputs and results will be exploited on short and long-term.

Based on the defined target groups and dissemination goals, the strategy aims to maximise the use of project outputs, create a network and a platform for the discussion on the future of European wildfire risk management (WFRM), engaging the entirety of the wildfire community.

The dissemination strategy of Firelogue described in this deliverable will be revised subsequently throughout the duration of the project. This will allow task leaders to adapt to future developments, address emerging challenges and subsequently implement lessons learned. As the project advances, the deliverable will be updated in months 24 and 36 to include additional events and dissemination activities. In addition, a successive review of the strategy will ensure a better understanding of our target groups and the adequate dissemination channels to reach them.

In the meantime, cooperation with other partners and IAs will stimulate collaboration, delivery of their key messages and dissemination activities will raise awareness about the importance of the project, support empowerment and engagement of users, groups and WFRM community.

THIS IS THE END OF THIS DOCUMENT

THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020
RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT NO 101036534